

Description of scurvy by Wierus (1567)

Summary by James Lind (1753)

In the 16th century, four European authors described the symptoms of scurvy in such a detail that the disease can be recognized as the disease we currently classify as scurvy: *Echtius* (1541), *Olaus Magnus* (1555), *Ronsseus* (1564), and *Wierus* (1567). Since these four texts are among the early unambiguous descriptions of scurvy, they have substantial historical relevance. All these texts were originally published in Latin. There are English translations of the sections of scurvy from the Olaus Magnus text. James Lind wrote English summaries of the texts of the three other authors. This document gives a brief background and a copy of Lind's summary of Wierus (1567) text on scurvy.

Various names of the author (1515–1588):

Johann Weyer "standard in German and English-language scholarship"

Ioannes Wierus

Johannes Wierius, Johannis Wieri, Johannes Wier, Joannes Wier, Jan Wier, Piscinarius

Wierus "was among the first to publish a thorough treatise against the trials and persecution of people accused of witchcraft"

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Johann_Weyer

https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Author%3AJohann_Weyer

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Johann_Weyer.png

<https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/term/BIOG219425>

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/P_Gg-4E-49

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/P_Bb-16-246

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM196008042630508>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1036613>

<https://doi.org/10.17077/0006-7474.1234>

<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781571137937.005>

<https://doi.org/10.1017/9789048541041>

Yellow is used to indicate the description of symptoms of scurvy.

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Background

James Lind (1753)¹ wrote, p.1

In the first accounts given us of this disease, by **Ronsseus**², **Echthius**³, and **Wierus**⁴, it is surprising to find, not only an accurate description of it, but an enumeration of almost all the truly antiscorbutic medicines that are known to the world even at this day.

James Lind p.3-5

But where *Wierus* transcribes the symptoms from this last author [*Echthius*], (which he does almost *verbatim*), upon this occasion he very justly differs from him. He observes, that the scurvy is not properly the *crisis* of a fever; but, like many other diseases, may be occasioned after it by unsound viscera, and a vitiated state of blood. He imagines people were induced to believe it a contagious malady, by seeing many whole families alike affected; but this he ascribed to the *sameness* of their diet. He was however deceived (probably by the authority of *Echthius*) in thinking, that where the gums were putrid, the disease might be infectious: and accordingly makes it a doubt, whether in some parts of the *Lower Germany*, where it had lately appeared, it was owing to their diet, or to infection. But it shall be fully proved hereafter, that the scurvy is not contagious or infectious.

It may be proper to observe further, that

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- 1 James Lind (1753). A Treatise of the Scurvy in Three Parts. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194> Selected sections of Lind's treatise. Lind's 1753 edition in scanned versions: <https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bg2gxrzz/items?canvas=7> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/xvi/mode/2up> <https://library.si.edu/digital-library/book/treatisescurvyt00lind>
 - 2 Ronsseus, see: Lind. Part III: Chapter II. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093314> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/356/mode/2up>
 - 3 Echthius, see: Lind. Part III: Chapter II. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093279> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/354/mode/2up>
 - 4 Wierus, see: Lind. v III: Chapter II. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093229> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/358/mode/2up>

Wierus had described the various and extraordinary symptoms of this malady, in so accurate a manner, that the succeeding authors for a long time did nothing more than copy him.

It was a considerable time afterwards, when

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Solomon Albertus wrote a large treatise on this subject, wherein he assumes great merit to himself in discovering a symptom not taken notice of by any author, and which he had once or twice observed in this disease, viz. a *rigor* or stiffness of the lower jaw. However, *Wierus* still continued in the greatest esteem and reputation; and his book was deemed the standard on this subject, even till the time of *Eugalenus*, who gives it that just character, and refers to it almost entirely for the cure. He must be allowed therefore to have been a good judge of this distemper: and as he was a person of eminent learning, as well as probity, (which his writings on this and many other subjects sufficiently shew), his word may be relied upon, when he tells us, that in his time this disease was peculiar to the inhabitants of the countries upon the north seas: he had never met with it in *Spain*, *France*, nor in *Italy*; nor was it to be seen in the large tract of *Upper Germany*: and as to *Asia* and *Africa*, if ever it appeared there, it would no doubt be in such places as lay adjacent to the sea; where such a situation, and a gross diet, with the use of putrid water, might give rise to it, in the same manner as they do in the countries where

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it was endemic. These were not conjectures in our author; for he was a great traveller, and had visited all the places he talks of. A book wrote in those times by him, *De praestigiis dæmonum*⁵, adds much to his reputation; as it shews he was neither so weak, nor credulous, as some later writers on the scurvy.

5 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/De_praestigiis_daemonum
<https://archive.org/details/depraestigiisdae00weye/page/n3/mode/2up>

James Lind p.11

So that whereas formerly the malady had a regular progression of symptoms in its different stages, accurately related by *Wierus* and many others, it became in *Eugalenus*'s time the most irregular and deceitful evil that we can well imagine.

James Lind p.52

[About *Willis*] But it will appear to any person who peruses the authors from whom he has borrowed the description of the symptoms, *wiz. Echthius, Wierus, &c.* that they described a very different disease from what *Willis* did. Dr *Willis*'s method of cure may perhaps be rationally applied to the diseases he described; but is by no means adapted to the disease characterised by the first writers on the scurvy.

James Lind p.63

As to the pathognomonic signs of this disease: If we compare its symptoms as described by *Echthius, Wierus*, and all other authors till the time of *Eugalenus* (a), with the accounts given of them in books of voyages, particularly the extraordinary narrative of what happened to the great Lord *Anson*'s crews in their passage round the world (b), we shall perceive an entire agreement in the essential signs of the distemper, (making a proper allowance for the different descriptions that may be expected from seamen and physicians), and appearances so singular as are not to be met with in any other. Thus, putrid gums, swelled legs, and spots, accompanying each other, and in their progress usually attended with rigid tendons in the ham, are observed in no other distemper.

James Lind p.352-355

... The author afterwards observes it to be the scurvy, a malady to which the northern nations, the *Dutch, &c.* are very subject; and upon this occasion, quoting a passage from *Olaus Magnus*⁶, says, "I have delighted myself

6 *Olaus Magnus* (1555) *Historia de gentibus septentrionalibus*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13380745> English translation of the sections on scurvy
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/A_Description_of_the_Northern_Peoples
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Olaus_Magnus

to recite the words of this author, because he speaketh thereof as being skilled, and has well described the disease; only he maketh no mention of the stiffening of the hams, nor of the superfluous flesh which groweth in the mouth.”

...

Olaus Magnus, in his history of the northern nations, published *ann.* 1555, observing what diseases are peculiar to them, gives us a long description of the scurvy.

...

Soon after we find three eminent physicians, all cotemporary, treating expressly of this distemper, *viz.*

Ronsseus, *Echthius*, and *Wierus*. To whom *Langius* may be added as a fourth, having wrote two epistles upon this subject. What is called *Echthius's Epitome*, was the first wrote, though the last published. It would appear from *Forrestus* to be a letter sent, in the year 1541, to *Blienburchius*, a physician at *Utrecht*; whose answer is now lost. The first book published expressly upon the scurvy was by *Ronsseus*, in the form of an epistle. The year is uncertain, as he afterwards corrected, and reprinted it in a different form. He is so modest as to say, that had he first seen *Wierus's* accurate observations, he would not have published any thing upon the subject. There is an edition of *Ronsseus* put down by *Mercklin* and *Lipenius*, in the year 1564; and of *Wierus's* observations in 1567. The learned Dr *Astruc* is of opinion, that these last were not published till 1580. It is thus far certain, that those authors corresponded together; and upon *Wierus* sending to *Ronsseus*, *Echthius's* letter, now called his *Epitome*, he published it, together with his own work, *Wierus's* observations, and two of *Langius's* epistles, in the year 1583.

James Lind p.445, Appendix

It has been no easy matter to obtain a knowledge of the many writings on this distemper. There have been collections made from time to time, of the several authors on the plague, venereal disease, &c. but no such have been compiled of writers on the scurvy. *Sennertus*, *ann.* 1624, when he wrote his own treatise, reprinted the writings of *Solomon Albertus* and *Martini*, together with *Ronsseus*, and the authors which he had published *ann.* 1583, *viz.* *Echthius*, *Wierus*, and *Langius*; and this book, containing those seven authors, is

the only collection ever published of writers on the scurvy.
There was here as little assistance to be obtained
from medical *bibliothecæ*.

August Hirsch (1885)⁷ wrote, p.513

Of somewhat later date are the first authentic accounts of the epidemic occurrence of scurvy on land... Shortly after there appeared the statements of **Olaus Magnus**, concerning the often observed epidemic prevalence of scurvy in the Scandinavian kingdoms, especially in times of famine; and about the same time, or a little later, the writings of **Echthius, Ronsseus, Wier**, Dodonaeus and Brucaeus, which testify to the comparatively common occurrence of the disease along the littoral of the North Sea and the Baltic...

These excellent descriptions of the malady, more especially by **Echthius, Ronsseus** and **Wier**, leave no doubt as to its nature [as scurvy].

Alfred Hess (1920)⁸ wrote, p.1-4

It is probable that scurvy existed in the northern parts of Europe and Asia ever since they were settled by man. We should hardly expect to have records of this condition, in view of the low educational status of the people, their greatly restricted literature, and their lack of intercourse with the people in the southern countries. In the sixteenth century, with the development and spread of education, we begin to hear of scurvy from various sources. **Olaus Magnus**, in his "History of the Northern Nations," published in 1555, described the disease which he tells us flourished among the soldiers in the camps and in the prisons.

About this time **Ronsseus, Echthius and Wierus** wrote special treatises on this disease, and recommended many dietary measures which we recognize to-day as most efficacious. The number of monographs on this subject multiplied with great rapidity in the course of the next twenty-five or fifty years; none of them, however, added anything essential to our knowledge...

7 Hirsch A (1885) Handbook of Geographical and Historical Pathology. Vol. II. Scurvy: pp.507-568.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10104179> Section on scurvy separately
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02hirsuoft/page/512/mode/2up>
https://archive.org/details/b28147455_0002/page/512/mode/2up
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02unse/page/512/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02hirs/page/512/mode/2up>

8 Hess AF (1920) Scurvy: Past and Present.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685195> Extracts relevant to the current context
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>
<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>

Anthony J Lorenz (1953)⁹ wrote:

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Lind makes the Dutch physician, **Balduin Ronsseus**, *facile princeps*¹⁰. Ronsseus¹¹ suggests that cold damp air of the sea and the seashore is the principal cause of scurvy. His is the first book written expressly on scurvy and was published in 1564. A later edition of Ronsseus (1585) combined the *epistolae* of **Echthius**¹² and Langius as well as the *observatio* of Wierus as a sort of compendium of the current views on scurvy. Ronsseus also held to the theory of involvement of the spleen in scurvy. Both Ronsseus and Echthius, writing separately, interpreted Pliny's description of the disease, which afflicted the Roman army under Germanicus, as scurvy.

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Wier (Wierus) (1567)¹³, copying Echthius, and Bruner (Brunerus) (1589), copying Wierus (adding only that leg pains preceded the actual onset of scurvy) well might have justified the subhead in Lind's preface *Dies Diem Docet*¹⁴, and the words:

“To know a disease and to cure it being the utmost essential things to be learned, I have, therefore, transcribed the symptoms and the cure of the scurvy from those authors where they do not entirely copy from each other. I hope such motives (truth, and good of mankind) will to the candid and to the most judicious be a sufficient apology for the liberties I have assumed”.

In re-reading the principal pre-Lind authors *seriatim* one observes the transitions from land to sea scurvy, or *purpura nautica*. One also sees the transition of the concept of scurvy as a winter epidemic among urban populations and its entity as a deficiency disease when studied in the isolation of the sailing ship when voyages of discovery increased in duration sufficient to permit complete deprivation of antiscorbutic stores.

9 <https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530062>

10 Facile princeps. Acknowledged leader.

11 Ronsseus, B. (1585). *De Magnis Hippocratis lienibits Plinique stomachace ac sceletyrbe, seu vulgo dicto scorbuto commentariolus. Accessere q'usdem epistolae quinque ejusdem argumenti, Joannis Echthii de scorbuto epitome, Joannis Wieri de scorbuto observatio. Joanna's Langii epistolae duae de scorbuto*. Wittenberg: C. Schleich.

12 Echthius, J. (1541). *De Scorbuto, vel Scorbutica Passione Epitome*. Cologne.

13 Wier (Wierus) J. (1567). *Medicarum Observationum Rararum Liber (I de Scorbuto)*. Basle: J. Oporinus.

14 Dies Diem Docet. The day teaches the day; one learns by experience.

The text on the following pages is the summary by Lind (1753, 1st ed.) p.359-361

<https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/358/mode/2up>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bg2gxrzz/items?canvas=381>

Jo. Wierus, chief physician to the Duke of Cleves and Juliers.

<https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/448/mode/2up>

The original in Latin:

Jo. Wieri medicarum observationum hactenus incognitarum lib. I. de scorbuto.

https://www.e-rara.ch/bau_1/doi/10.3931/e-rara-44

https://www.e-rara.ch/bau_1/download/pdf/38282

https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_-FqKIF7hHB4C/mode/2up

<https://archive.org/details/hin-wel-all-00002888-001/page/n58/mode/2up>

https://books.google.fi/books/about/Medicarum_observatum_rararum_liber_1.html?id=xIs8AAAAcAAJ

https://books.google.fi/books/about/Joannis_Wieri_Medicarum_observatum_ra.html?id=RFXRiSi36D0C

“Ioannis Wieri. De scorbuto tractatus”, p.187-205.

<https://archive.org/details/descorbutotracta00senn/page/186/mode/2up>

https://www.google.com/books/edition/De_scorbuto_tractatus/W7w_AAAAcAAJ

https://www.google.com/books/edition/De_scorbuto_tractatus_Acc_ejusdem_argume/f2RWAAAAcAAJ

A.D. 1567

Jo. Wieri medicarum observationum hactenus incognitarum lib. I. de scorbuto.

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He transcribes all the symptoms out of *Echthius* at great length, with the following additions. The weakness in the legs felt upon the approach of the disease, is attended with a stiffness there, and a small pain. The flesh of the gums is often destroyed to the roots of the teeth. Smaller spots, resembling blood sprinkled upon the part, (or flea-bites, but larger), appear on the legs, thighs, and on the whole body; but the very large, livid, and purple spots, chiefly on the legs. Sometimes this livid colour will shew itself in the *fauces*¹⁵ of those who are near death. In the progress of the disease, the tendons of the legs become stiff and contracted. Some are seized with a slow erratic fever. After ardent malignant fevers, and double tertians, ill cured, he has known the scurvy to follow; upon which a malignant quartan has ensued. This still left the scurvy behind it; which was at last cured by the proper method. When the legs are greatly swelled, they are sometimes altogether of a livid colour. The pulse, as in a quartan fever, varies: so that at different times, and according to the state of the disease, it is small, hard, quick, and weak. The urine is reddish, turbid, thick, and fæculent, like new red wine, resembling that which is usual in the fit of a quartan when sweating; and of a bad smell. He adds afterwards, in his prognostics, that if ulcers break out on the *tibia*, they are with great difficulty healed up; being extremely fœtid, of a gangrenous

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disposition, and so putrid, as not to feel the application of a hot iron.

He assigns as causes of this distemper, unwholesome air, such bad and corrupt food as was used in the northern countries, and by their shipping, viz. stinking pork, smoked rancid bacon, mouldy bread, thick fæculent ale, bad water, melancholy and grief of mind, preceeding fevers, the stoppage of usual evacuations, &c.

Though he sometimes bleeds in the cure, yet he forbids it when the disease is advanced. In this case, after evacuating the *primæ viæ* by a lenient of *senna*, or the like, (observing that it does not bear violent purgatives),

15 Fauces. The opening at the back of the mouth into the throat.

the patient is to be sweated twice a-day, viz. in the morning, and at four after noon, with a draught of four ounces of the expressed juices of the antiscorbutic herbs; which are, *cochlearia*, *nasturtium aq. et nasturtium hyber.* of each equal parts, with but half the quantity of *becabunga*; adding a little cinnamon and sugar. The proportion of the different ingredients may be diminished or increased, according to the constitution of the patient, state of the disease, and heat of the body. He would have the herbs always fresh and green when used; and they may sometimes be boiled in goats or cows milk, or rather in whey: but their expressed juice mixed with whey, is preferable to their decoction. He sometimes adds *absinth. vulgare*, *fumaria*, *chamædrys*, and, in certain cases, *nummularia*. To people who are fond of a *farrago* of medicines, he gives a long list of all the antiscorbutic and aperient herbs, roots, seeds, &c. to which later authors have made but a small addition; and remarks, that he generally made successful cures by a proper use of a few of these plants. The following remedy he understood had cured many.

R *absinth. vulg. sicc. bacc. juniper. contus. ana manip. i. lact. caprin. lib. iv. Coq. ad tertiæ partis consumptionem.* A dram of saffron is to be infused in the strained decoction, and a warm draught taken three times a-day. After giving
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some other cures usual in his time for this distemper, he observes, that there is nothing specific in the common antiscorbutic herbs, as they are called; but that all acrid plants which incide and attenuate, as also many aperient roots, and warm seeds, are highly serviceable. At the same time, a diet of easy digestion, and similar intention, must be used, with good sound ale or wine with wormwood infused, or milk and whey. Care must be taken to procure dry chearful lodgings, and to banish grief, cares, &c.

He afterwards subjoins various topical applications for the different symptoms. For the putrid gums, R *sal. mar. alum. ana dr. ii. aq. font. lib. i. M. Bulliant simul.* The people of *Friesland* use the following. R *acet. cerevis. lib. ii. bol. armen. unc. ss. alumin. dr. ii. mellis unc. iii. M. Bulliant simul.* The Saxons add to the former, *herba sabina*. If the putrefaction is very great, *ung. Ægyptiac.* or *alum. ust.* mixed with honey, may be used;

or it is to be stopped by touching with *ol. vitriol*.¹⁶

In his appendix, he particularly recommends whey for the cure of this disease; and gives a description, at great length, of the *cochlearia*, and some other antiscorbutic herbs.

16 Oil of Vitriol. Sulfuric acid.

”Sulfuric acid, known in antiquity as oil of vitriol”

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vitriol>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sulfuric_acid

Elixir of vitriol: A mixture of sulfuric acid and alcohol, once prescribed as a treatment for scurvy.

https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/elixir_of_vitriol